

values for various forms of soil N (0-15 cm depth) before transplanting are given in Table 1. The values show that a major part of organic N was present in acid hydrolyzable N form (59–74%) and nonhydrolyzable N constituted 26–41% of the total N present. Hexosamines represented 1.9–7.1% and amino acids 10.7–16.7% of total N. Hydrolyzable

NH₄-N constituted 10.6–13.9% of total N present.

Total N, hydrolyzable N, and nonhydrolyzable N correlated significantly with yield and N uptake by rice variety PR106 (Table 2). Among the forms of hydrolyzable N, NH₄-N showed the highest significant relationship with relative yield ($r =$

0.64*) and relative N uptake ($r = 0.72^{**}$), followed by hexosamine N ($r = 0.61^*$, 0.60^*) and amino acid N ($r = 0.60^*$, 0.43). Results show that forms of both hydrolyzable N and nonhydrolyzable N supply N to rice plants. Among the various fractions of soil N, hydrolyzable NH₄-N seemed to be more important. □

Rapid and sensitive method to estimate salinity tolerance of *Azolla pinnata*

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We have developed a rapid, nondestructive but sensitive method for assessing the salinity tolerance of different strains of *Azolla pinnata*. Pigments (chlorophyll and phycocyanin) are measured by their fluorescence in the heterocysts and the vegetative cells of *Anabaena azolla* isolated from sodium chloride-treated azolla, using Leitz fluorescence microscope. Chlorophyll and phycocyanin were reduced in both types of cells (see figure). The acetylene reduction activity of the *Azolla-Anabaena* complex also showed reduction, which correlated with that in the pigments of the endophyte.

Measuring the chlorophyll and phycocyanin content of *Anabaena* isolated from salt-treated azolla can be used to estimate the salinity tolerance of a particular strain of azolla. □

Effect of salinity on chlorophyll and phycocyanin of *Anabaena azollae*, and on acetylene reduction activity, Baroda, India. Sodium chloride levels: 1 = 10 mM, 2 = 20 mM, 3 = 30 mM, and 4 = 40 mM.

Effect of azolla and inorganic N combined

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We studied the effect of azolla and inorganic N on growth and yield of lowland rice variety Co 43 during 1983–84 wet and dry seasons. Soil was clay loam, with 261 kg available N/ha,

15.9 kg P/ha, 460.7 kg K/ha, and pH 7.9. The design was a randomized block with four replications. Seedlings were transplanted at 30 d at 20 × 10-cm spacing.

Prilled urea (PU) or urea supergranules (USG) alone or in combination with azolla at 75:25 were compared. N rate was 100 kg/ha for all the treatments except control. PU was split-applied: 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation stages;

USG was applied all basal, point placed, 1 wk after transplanting. Superphosphate at 22 kg P/ha and muriate of potash at 42 kg K/ha were basally applied. Azolla was incorporated 1 wk before transplanting.

USG at 100 kg N/ha or azolla at 25 kg N/ha with USG at 75 kg N/ha were equal in increasing dry matter production, number of panicles, grain numbers, and grain and straw yields in both seasons (see table). □

Effect of azolla and inorganic N on rice.^a Coimbatore, India, 1983-84

Treatment ^b	1983 wet season					1983-84 dry season				
	Dry matter production (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Dry matter production (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Control (no N)	6.4 d	245 d	69 d	2.5 d	4.0 d	6.1 d	212 d	63 d	2.3 d	4.0 d
100 kg N-PU	13.4 b	502 b	91 b	5.9 b	7.7 b	13.1 b	483 b	83 bc	5.5 b	7.6 b
25 kg N-azolla+ 75 kg N-PU	11.0 c	413 c	88 c	5.0 c	6.4 c	10.7 c	397 c	80 c	4.5 c	6.2 c
100 kg N-USG	15.2 a	618 a	100 a	7.0 a	9.0 a	14.8 a	598 a	87 ab	6.5 a	8.4 a
25 kg N-azolla + 75 kg N-USG	15.1 a	565 a	100 a	7.0 a	8.9 a	14.6 a	560 a	89 a	6.4 a	8.4 a

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bN rate = 100 kg/ha.

Effect of cultivation method on the rice crop and the mechanical impediment of Vertisols

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Puddling for transplanted rice facilitates transplanting, maintenance of submergence, and weed control. But in Vertisols, with low infiltration rates, puddling disturbs the soil physical condition and creates problems for field preparation of dry season wheat.

We studied the influence of different cultivation methods on the rice crop and soil mechanical impediment. Treatments — direct drilling (DD), direct transplanting (DT), bullock puddling (BP), and tractor puddling (TP) — were in a randomized block design with four

Table 1. Effect of puddling on penetration force. Jabalpur, India, 1985.

Treatment	Depth (m)	Penetration force (kg/cm ²)	
		Tillering stage	Milk stage
Direct drilling	5	1.49	4.61
	10	4.93	6.26
	15	6.49	7.36
Direct transplanting	5	2.15	4.85
	10	5.30	6.24
	15	6.39	7.49
Bullock puddling	5	1.37	2.74
	10	3.31	6.01
	15	4.37	7.35
Tractor puddling	5	1.02	2.80
	10	4.47	6.18
	15	6.02	7.43

Table 2. Effect of method of cultivation on growth and yield of paddy. Jabalpur, India, 1985.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		Plant height (cm)	Tillers/Plant	Panicle length (cm)
	Grain	Straw			
Direct drilling	4.2	10.6	76.8	6.3	20.8
Direct transplanting	3.3	8.4	75.6	6.4	21.2
Bullock puddling	3.7	9.2	77.8	6.4	21.2
Tractor puddling	3.4	9.4	72.0	6.3	21.3
CD at 0.05	0.7	1.5	ns	ns	no
cv (%)	28	19	—	—	—

replications. Rice variety Ratna was sown 7 Nov 1985. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-40 kg NPK/ha.

Plant height, tiller numbers, panicle length, and grain and straw yields were recorded. Penetration force at tillering and milk stages was measured by penetrometer.

DD gave the highest mechanical impediment (MI), and TP the lowest, irrespective of growth stage (Table 1). The increased magnitude of MI at the

milk stage was attributed to reduced moisture content.

Tillers/ plant, plant height, and panicle length did not differ significantly (Table 2). DD gave the significantly highest grain and straw yield. The differences among DT, BP, and TP were not significant. A similar trend was found with straw yield.

Reduced yield due to puddling is attributed to deterioration of physical conditions of the soil. □

Efficiency of nitrogen fertilizers and a nitrification inhibitor

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We studied the relative efficiency of urea, ammonium sulfate, and potassium nitrate during 1986 kharif (Jun-Sep). Nitrification inhibitor 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole (ATC) was applied at 5% by weight of urea. To restrict NH₃ volatilization, urea-nitrification inhibitor and urea alone treatments were applied

in bands (3 cm below surface) between the rows. N at 110 kg/ha was applied in 3 equal splits: 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting with no standing water.

Soil of the experimental field was Fatehpur loamy sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.5, 0.23% organic C, 7 kg Olsen's P/ha and 71 kg ammonium acetate extractable K/ha. Soil percolation rate was about 6 mm/h. Treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Six-week-old seedlings of rice variety PR106 were transplanted the third week of June. □